

WD-XRF method for rapid analysis of macro and micronutrient uptake in maize grain upon foliar application of seaweed sap formulations

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Abstract : In the present article, a wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WD-XRF) method is described for rapid analysis of macro (P, K, Ca, Mg and S) and micronutrients (B, Zn, Cl, Mn, Cu and Na) in maize grains upon foliar application of seaweed sap. The method is simple and fast as it involves drying, pulverising and pressing of maize grains in order to determine the elemental composition. Powdering of the grain with advanced ball mill not only offers suitable particle size and homogeneity of the sample but also rapidity as compared to the simple mill/mortar and pestle. The range of expanded uncertainty for macronutrients ranges from 0.010 to 0.180% while for micronutrient it is 0.45 to 47.44 mg/kg. The calibration and validation was done by using biological Certified Reference Materials (CRMs). True-ness of the results was examined by comparing experimentally obtained values of the elements against the certified values. The seaweed sap is tested as a plant growth stimulant as a part of multi-institutional and multi-locational trial across different states of India in different crops.

Keywords : WD-XRF, macronutrients, micronutrients, maize, seaweed sap.

Introduction

X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) spectrometry is a well-established analytical technique for elemental analysis of a wide variety of solid and liquid samples¹⁻⁵. Major, minor and trace elements can be qualitatively and quantitatively determined in various kinds of samples like minerals/ores⁶, Petroleum substances⁷, nuclear materials^{8,9}, pharmaceutical/medical¹⁰⁻¹², environmental¹³⁻¹⁶ and biological materials¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Features like multi-element analysis, fast speed, economy, easy of automation and versatility have made it mature technique for analytical support in research laboratories and as well as for routine quality control in many industries. One of the remarkable features of this technique is its non-destructiveness which does not require any sample pre-treatment unlike for FAAS (Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry), ETAAS (Electrothermal Atomic Absorption Spectrometry), ICP-OES (Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry) and ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry). It requires powdering and pelletizing (with or without binder) of solid samples in order to determine the elemental composition. As the solid sample analysis

is not associated with the use of harmful acid or mixture of acids for its preparation, it can be termed as environmental-friendly technique. Developments in the detection performance²⁰, instrumentation of X-ray techniques/optics, new quantification models, preconcentration methods²¹, spectrum analysis, specimen preparation^{22,23}, matrix correction, calibration and applications^{24,25} are well documented in the literature. Development and commercialization of field-portable and bench top XRF spectrometers offers compact design and simplicity of operation with a low cost gives wide applicability²⁶⁻²⁹. Reference-free XRF analysis is also feasible, which provides the results within the frame of its uncertainties^{30,31}. Specimen preparation could be the source of the errors in X-ray fluorescence analysis²². XRF analysis of powdered sample requires to have a uniform particle size, and to have a grain size small enough to avoid particle-size effect problems. For a routine XRF analysis, a particle size of less than 40 μm is commonly acceptable¹.

As the extracts derived from seaweeds are biodegradable, non-toxic, non-polluting and non-hazardous to hu-

mans, animals and birds³², it is one of the viable options as biofertilizer against chemical-based fertilizers³³. It contains major and minor nutrients, amino acids, vitamins³⁴ and Plant Growth Regulators (PGRs)³⁵. It can be applied to crops as foliar sprays, soil drenches or root dips. Its use on plants can increase nutrient uptake from soil³⁶. Recently, improved crop quality and nutrient uptake for nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium was observed for green gram with seaweed extract applications³⁷. The objective of the present work is to apply WD-XRF method for rapid analysis of macro and micronutrient uptake in maize grain upon foliar application of seaweed sap formulations.

Equipments and instruments :

Ball mill : To obtain fine powder having suitable particle size from grain, advanced ball mill supplied by Fritsch, Germany (Pulverisette-5) was operated at 300 rpm (rotation per minute) for 10 min.

Pelletizer : Pelletizer (hydraulic pressing machine) manufactured and supplied by Kimaya Engineers, Thane, Maharashtra (India) was used.

Particle size analyzer : The particle size analysis (as dry powder) of the sample was done on Malvern Instrument (Mastersizer 2000) at the feed rate of 40%. It can measure the particle size range from 0.02–2000 μm . Fine powder obtained from ball mill was analyzed for particle size.

Scanning electron microscope : To examine the homogeneity and particle size of the sample through images, SEM (LEO 1430 VP) was used.

X-Ray fluorescence spectrometer : Elemental concentrations were determined by WD-XRF spectrometer, S4 Pioneer (Bruker AXS, Germany) equipped with advanced optical systems, two detectors, different copper foils as filters, 4–5 different analyzing crystals, an X-ray tube with an Rh anode, auto sampler for 60 samples and SPECTRA^{plus} software.

Materials and methods :

Extraction of sap from Kappaphycus alvarezii : Freshly harvested *Kappaphycus alvarezii* red seaweed cultivated in the south east coast of India (9°15'N, 78°58'E) was crushed and filtered to obtain pristine sap which was stored with preservatives as reported previously³⁸.

Sample collection and storage : Maize grains were collected from College Agronomy Farm, B. A. College of Agriculture, Anand Agricultural University, Anand (Gujarat). Maize grains were allowed for drying in a contaminated-free area. Recommended containers made of non-wettable material such as Teflon, was used for storage and transportation of grains.

Sample preparation : After assuring suitable particle size and homogeneity, 3 g of the sample mixed with 1 g boric acid (AR grade, S.D. fine chemicals) as binder. During pellet preparation operations great care was taken and dust-free environment was chosen to avoid sample contamination. Pressed pellets were prepared using 40 mm die set and 40 mm aluminium cups filled with the sample with boric acid as binder at 20 tons pressure with 10 second of dwelling time.

Calibration : Measurement conditions like analyte line, detector, crystal, X-ray tube power etc. were optimised for each element. Optimization is achieved by repeated analysis of CRMs and correction of the variables in order to achieve elemental concentration close to certified value. Details of measurement conditions are given in Table 1. To carry out the calibration of each element it is necessary to use Certified Reference Materials (CRMs). For calibration, the CRMs used are SRM 1515 Apple Leaves, SRM 1573a Tomato Leaves with elements namely Na, K, Ca, Mg, B, Mn, Cl, Fe, P, Cu, S and Zn. These CRMs were supplied by National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), USA. Calibration curves for these elements were constructed and necessary corrections were done with the help of SPECTRA^{plus} software. Experimental results obtained for the Certified Reference Materials (CRMs), together with their uncertainty (u_m) are given in Tables 2 and 3.

Results and discussion

Biological materials like powered grain are generally heterogeneous. When dealing with solid samples, drying, powdering, and homogeneity testing is necessary before preparing the samples for measurement. The average particle size distribution of the samples obtained from particle size analyzer ranges from 27–40 μm which is within the acceptable size of 40 μm . Scanning electron microscopic imaging shows the particle size ranges from 10–

Table 1. Measurement conditions of each element analyzed by WD-XRF instrument (OVO-55, W/Si multilayer, PET, pentaerythrite, LiF200, lithium fluoride)

Element	Analyte line angle (2θ)	Measurement	Detector	Crystal	Line energy (KeV)	Net intensity (KCps)	Wavelength (Å)	Tube (kV)	Tube (mA)
Na	Kα	24.738	Flow	OVO-55	1.0410	0.3624	11.910	27	150
K	Kα	136.682	Flow	LiF200	3.3139	222.9	3.7414	50	81
Ca	Kα	112.89	Flow	LiF200	3.6918	219.9	3.3584	50	81
Mg	Kα	20.499	Flow	OVO-55	1.2533	9.700	9.8930	27	150
B	Kα	40.760	Flow	OVO-B	0.1830	0.6660	67.749	27	150
Mn	Kα	63.037	Scintillation	LiF200	5.8989	3.558	2.1018	60	67
Cl	Kα	65.411	Flow	PET	2.6225	4.606	4.7278	27	150
Fe	Kα	57.629	Scintillation	LiF200	6.4041	6.011	1.9360	60	67
P	Kα	89.432	Flow	PET	2.0137	8.951	6.1570	27	150
Cu	Kα	45.250	Flow	LiF200	8.0481	15.21	1.5406	60	67
S	Kα	75.749	Scintillation	PET	2.3079	18.16	5.3722	27	150
Zn	Kα	42.190	Scintillation	LiF200	8.6392	20.97	1.4352	60	67

Table 2. Results obtained for the Certified Reference Material SRM 1515 (Apple leaves) by WD-XRF instrument

Element	SRM 1515 (Apple leaves)			
	Certified value	Value obtained by WD-XRF	Δm	U _{Δm}
P ^a	0.159 ± 0.011	0.168 ± 0.002	0.009	0.022
K ^a	1.61 ± 0.02	1.63 ± 0.044	0.020	0.097
Ca ^a	1.526 ± 0.015	1.549 ± 0.08	0.023	0.032
Mg ^a	0.271 ± 0.008	0.270 ± 0.0046	0.001	0.018
S ^a	0.180*	0.182	0.002	-
Cu ^b	5.64 ± 0.24	5.57 ± 0.2022	0.070	0.627
Zn ^b	12.5 ± 0.3	15.71 ± 0.645	3.21	6.137
B ^b	27 ± 2	28.14 ± 0.260	1.14	4.032
Cl ^b	579 ± 23	586 ± 5.814	5.814	47.44
Na ^b	24.4 ± 1.2	21.71 ± 1.10	2.68	3.26

^aConcentrations are expressed as percentage (%) while ^bas mg/kg. Δm is the absolute value of difference between value obtained by WD-XRF and certified value. *Means non-certified values.

Table 3. Results obtained for the Certified Reference Material SRM 1573a (Tomato leaves) by WD-XRF instrument

Element	SRM 1573a (Tomato leaves)			
	Certified value	Value obtained by WD-XRF	Δm	U _{Δm}
P ^a	0.216 ± 0.004	0.224 ± 0.00324	0.008	0.010
K ^a	2.70 ± 0.05	2.76 ± 0.024	0.06	0.110
Ca ^a	5.05 ± 0.09	5.08 ± 0.009	0.031	0.180
Mg ^a	1.2*	1.210	0.010	-
S ^a	0.96*	0.965	0.005	-
Cu ^b	4.70 ± 0.14	4.71 ± 0.184	0.01	0.456
Zn ^b	30.9 ± 0.7	28.71 ± 0.1	2.19	2.37
B ^b	33.3 ± 0.7	35.28 ± 0.808	1.98	2.139
Cl ^b	6600	6621	21.0	-
Na ^b	136 ± 4	137.85 ± 1.45	1.85	8.51
Mn ^b	246 ± 8	242.71 ± 1.01	3.29	16.12

^aConcentrations are expressed as percentage (%) while ^bas mg/kg. Δm is the absolute value of difference between value obtained by WD-XRF and certified value. *Means non-certified values.

14 μm and there is homogeneity of the size distribution (Fig. 1). Both particle size and homogeneity are crucial parameters as these may affect the emission intensity during XRF analysis^{39,40}.

Calculation of the limit of detection (L_D) and quantification (L_Q): The sample was measured seven times under reproducibility conditions and L_D and L_Q were calculated as per the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) guidelines using the following expressions^{41,42} and their values are given in Table 4 :

$$L_D = 3.29 \cdot \sigma \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. SEM images to examine the homogeneity and particle size (left) 20 μm and (right) 10 μm scale for powdered maize grain.

Table 4. L_D and L_Q of the elements analysed by WD-XRF

Element	L_D	L_Q
P ^a	0.0174	0.053
K ^a	0.210	0.640
Ca ^a	0.069	0.211
Mg ^a	0.04	0.124
Cu ^b	1.60	4.87
Zn ^b	5.6	17.0
Mn ^b	8.85	26.90
B ^b	2.26	6.88
Cl ^b	50.50	153.5
Na ^b	2.68	29.27

^aConcentrations are expressed as percentage (%) while ^bas mg/kg.

$$L_Q = 10 \cdot \sigma \quad (2)$$

where σ is the value of standard deviation of the measurements.

Uncertainty (u_m), absolute value of difference between experimental values and certified value (Δm), combined uncertainty of the experimental result and certified value ($u_{\Delta m}$) and expanded uncertainty ($U_{\Delta m}$) are calculated⁴³ as follows :

$$u_m = \sigma / \sqrt{N} \quad (3)$$

where N = number of measurement of the sample under reproducibility conditions.

$$\Delta m = |C_{\text{exp}} - C_{\text{certi}}| \quad (4)$$

where C_{exp} = experimentally obtained concentration and C_{certi} = certified concentration.

$$u_{\Delta m} = \sqrt{u_{\text{exp}}^2 + u_{\text{certi}}^2} \quad (5)$$

where u_{exp} and u_{certi} are experimental and certified uncertainty respectively.

The expanded uncertainty ($U_{\Delta m}$) is obtained by multiplying $u_{\Delta m}$ by a coverage factor (k), generally equals to 2, which corresponds approximately to a 95% level of confidence. Thus :

$$U_{\Delta m} = 2 \cdot u_{\Delta m} \quad (6)$$

In order to verify the goodness of the method, Δm is compared with $U_{\Delta m}$, such that if $\Delta m < U_{\Delta m}$, there is no significant difference between the experimental value and the certified value. The results are presented in Tables 2 and 3. The uncertainty value of sulphur for both of the CRMs and Mg for SRM 1573a (Tomato leaves) were not

given the certificate of analysis, therefore $U_{\Delta m}$ for these elements were not calculated. As $\Delta m < U_{\Delta m}$ for all the elements, thus validating the applied method of analysis. Elemental analysis of plant samples can be helpful to monitor their development, diseases and nutrient values. In the present study macro- and micronutrients in maize grain have been determined upon foliar application of seaweed sap, after validation of the analytical method. Maize crop of rabi season 2012-2013, grown under control (untreated) and seaweed sap treated was utilised for the study. Foliar sprays of seaweed sap formulations of different concentrations (2.5, 5, 10 and 15%) were applied to the crop just prior to the critical growth stages along with recommended dose of fertilizer (150-50-0 N.P.K. kg/ha). All the samples were prepared in four replicates and their average nutrient values are given in Table 5.

The seaweed sap was tested as a plant growth stimulant as a part of multi-institutional and multi-locational trial across 20 states of India in different crops. At most of the places there were positive response to the application of seaweed sap as a foliar spray, however, at a very few places, response to seaweed sap application was not observed and no improvement in grain yield was observed when the sap was sprayed over maize. The trial conducted at the field of Anand (AAU) where the sap was sprayed 3 times over the crop growing season at 5 dilutions of the seaweed sap (0, 2.5, 5, 10 and 15%). All the treatments received sap sprays over and above the recommended dose of fertilizers. This was probably due to differential varietal response, and the test variety of maize in this case did not respond positively to seaweed sap. In order to correlate the yield behaviour with grain nutrient content, the analysis of grain sample was done. It can be observed that there were no significant differences with respect to nutrient content in grain for most of the nutrients except that of sodium and chloride concentration, which somehow increased considerably by application of sap at higher concentration (>5%). The constituents in the sap probably did not affect this variety of maize in stimulating the uptake of most of the nutrients while sodium content was stimulated. These results thus corroborate the yield response obtained in this variety of maize. In conclusion, we have described a WD-XRF method for rapid analysis of macro- and micronutrient uptake in maize grain upon foliar application of seaweed sap formulations.

Table 5. Macro and micronutrient values determined by WD-XRF upon various treatments (T1-T4) of seaweed sap on maize grain

Element	Untreated (RDF + water spray)	T1 (2.5% sap + RDF)	T2 (5.0% sap + RDF)	T3 (10.0% sap + RDF)	T4 (15.0% sap + RDF)
P ^a	0.382	0.382	0.382	0.380	0.382
K ^{a*}	0.484	0.484	0.483	0.489	0.470
Ca ^{a*}	0.021	0.023	0.022	0.022	0.021
Mg ^{a*}	0.081	0.079	0.077	0.075	0.077
S ^a	0.119	0.120	0.119	0.120	0.118
Cu ^b	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
Zn ^b	43.7	44.2	44.2	44.5	44.2
Mn ^b	265.5	265.2	268.7	268.2	266.7
B ^b	44.0	45.5	45.2	45.0	47.0
Cl ^b	625.7	645.5	634.5	643.0	682.0
Na ^b	4.0	4.0	15.5	13.2	39.5

^aConcentrations are expressed as percentage (%) while ^bas mg/kg. RDF means Recommended Dose of Fertilizer. *K, Ca and Mg are present below L_Q and the results obtained may not be highly reliable but we have incorporated the data to give some idea about it to the readers.

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